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From pollution to solution: a call for source control strategies for microplastics in the Ocean

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E-mail: juliana.ivardosul@io-warnemuende.de**Keywords:** research field advances, avenues for future research, synthetic polymers, plastic cycle, timeline

1. Motivation

Ten years ago, the research field of microplastics in marine environments was not yet established as a significant area of focus within the broader field of environmental contaminants of emerging concern. This is no longer the case; microplastics research has reached a point of maturity in its investigative approach as evidenced by the predicted number of publications on the subject (Halden 2015). The representation of microplastics pollution in the media has also increased over time, influencing individual awareness, public debate, behaviour and political decisions (Pop *et al* 2023). Consequently, microplastics feature prominently within the United Nations (UN) Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021–2030), a 10-year framework initiative to identify, generate and utilise critical knowledge for the sustainable management of the oceans.

In this perspective article, I revisit a literature review published 10 years ago, in 2014 (Ivar do Sul and Costa 2014), and use it as a benchmark paper to identify gaps in microplastic knowledge, key themes, and approaches highlighted in the paper's *conclusion and suggestions* section. Ivar do Sul and Costa (2014) was one of the first exploratory literature reviews on microplastics pollution in the marine environment, with subsequent research leading to the publication of several hundred review articles on microplastics pollution. Next, I compare microplastics research pre- and post-2014 in order to gain insight into the evolution of knowledge over the past decade, and to highlight persisting challenges faced by the microplastics research community. Finally, I discuss how aspects related to source control strategies align with the mission of the UN Ocean Decade. Please note that

the objective of this study is not to replicate existing literature on the subject.

2. Microplastics research pre-2014

At the time of the publication of the benchmark paper in 2014, microplastics research was still in its infancy. To illustrate, approximately 100 papers were reviewed and critically discussed in the benchmark paper to present the current state of microplastics research. The analysis revealed that 80% of the publications were published within a 15-year window, between 1999 and 2013, while 60% were published within a five-year window, between 2009 and 2013. This rapid growth in the number of published articles in the field of microplastics research marked the first appearance of an exponential increase in microplastics research activity.

At the time, an upper limit of 5 mm had been unofficially adopted for the identification of microplastics within the scientific community. The limit was inclusive of plastic pellets, which are relatively straightforward to identify and count. However, it does not adhere to the standard prefix *micro* employed within the metric system. Sampling strategies employed at the time were largely inherited from previous studies rather than designed specifically for microplastics research. For instance, 300 μm zooplankton nets were the most commonly used method for sampling microplastics in marine environments because they were available. Furthermore, opportunistic sampling during research with alternative objectives had revealed the *in situ* ingestion of microplastics by fish, seabirds, and other vertebrates. Despite being irregularly distributed in space and time, these initial studies were able to provide

Figure 1. Numbers of annual peer-reviewed papers on microplastics published from 2014 to 2023. Numbers result from the exploratory literature review search conducted using the WoS research platform. For comparison with numbers pre-2014 please referred to Ivar do Sul and Costa (2014).

valuable insights into the extent of microplastics pollution across marine ecosystems (Ivar do Sul and Costa 2014).

3. Microplastics research post-2014

In order to gain insight into the subsequent literature published in the field following the 2014 benchmark paper, an exploratory literature search was conducted using the Web of Science (WoS) research platform. The search query included the following keywords and Boolean operators: ‘microplastic*’ (title) AND ‘marine environment’ OR ‘marine pollution’ OR ‘sea water’ OR ‘marine sediments’ (topic) NOT ‘nanoplastic*’ (topic). This query returned >4400 results from the WoS core collection. The analysis revealed that approximately 50% of the publications were published within a three-year window, between 2021 and 2023, while approximately 20% were published in 2023 alone (figure 1). This indicates that publications within the microplastics research field are currently undergoing an even steeper increase than it was 10 years ago.

The upper limit for defining microplastic sizes continues to be unofficially set at 5 mm. However, a smaller range of 10 μm –1 mm has been receiving considerable support from the scientific community in the last couple of years (Hartmann *et al* 2019, Chae *et al* 2023). The proposed smaller range of microplastic sizes excludes smaller (1–10 μm) microplastics that are extremely challenging to extract and analyse for environmental samples, and also relatively larger plastics (>1 mm) that do not penetrate cell walls and may have limited toxic effects compared to smaller ones. This interval is also consistent with the metric system standard nomenclature.

The development of refined sampling methods to sample microplastics in lower size ranges (i.e. <500 μm or smaller) are now operational at sea and in rivers (Cutroneo *et al* 2020). For instance, pumping

systems to sample pelagic microplastics have been developed to be free from contamination from the surrounding air, from the instrument itself, or from the sampling procedure, and represent a legacy of the microplastics research community (e.g. Lenz and Labrenz 2018). Furthermore, regular monitoring campaigns rather than opportunistic samplings reveal microplastics bioaccumulation within each trophic level, with virtually all animal groups being studied (Parolini *et al* 2023). The sampling methods that have been developed have also enabled the investigation of significant environmental impacts of microplastics in a diverse range of matrices beyond the marine environment, including the effects of microplastics exposure on human health.

4. Achievements and decade-long research challenges

Microplastics have been demonstrated to be a significant environmental pollutant, as evidenced by a substantial body of research (see Thompson *et al* 2024 for recent discussion). Since the publication of the 2014 benchmark paper, considerable progress has been made. Some of the issues identified in the *conclusion and suggestions* section of the 2014 benchmark paper have now become firmly established in the scientific community. These include the investigation of microplastics in Antarctic and Arctic habitats, where a range of studies are now available (Gurumoorthi and Luis 2023); the chemical characterisation of microplastics to confirm its composition, which is a non-negotiable prerequisite when smaller target microplastics are not easily discerned from natural particles (Ivar do Sul 2021); and the investigation of microplastics ingestion through laboratory tests to verify physical harm to marine life (Egbeocha *et al* 2018). On occasion, the general hypothesis that microplastic fibres cause pervasive effects on biota has been refuted (Klasios *et al* 2024). Other research has found that

non-synthetic particles may induce physical effects similar to those of microplastics when ingested by invertebrates (Putri *et al* 2021). It is therefore recommended that non-synthetic particles within the same size range (e.g. wool fibres, sand grains) should also be tested together with microplastics in laboratory-focused studies in order to exclude any potential bias.

Despite the progress, unresolved gaps have persisted for at least a decade. While methods for quantifying microplastics from environmental matrices have been refined, there is still a lack of standardised protocols, which makes comparisons between methods and results challenging (Reineccius and Waniek 2024). This ultimately limits the capacity to diagnose microplastics pollution on a large scale and over an extended period of time. For example, standardizing measurements in mass units (e.g. grams per volume or grams per body weight) would improve comparability and facilitate broader analyses. Also, with few exceptions, microplastics have yet to be incorporated into routine monitoring programs in rivers and in the ocean. This is a consequence of the fact that the most widely used particle-based methodologies (i.e. when particles are visually or numerically counted) are time-consuming, expensive and difficult for utilisation within standard monitoring systems. A solution is to employ mass-based methods such as pyrolysis coupled with gas chromatography-mass spectrometry to quantitatively analyse trace levels of plastic polymers. The use of mass-based methodologies would enable the comparison of microplastic amounts with other organic compounds that are measured in a dissolved form (e.g. persistent organic pollutants).

A further decade-long research challenge is to estimate the relative importance of primary and secondary origins of microplastics. Primary microplastics enter the environment with a defined size and shape, whether secondary microplastics result from the fragmentation of larger plastics in the environment. The prevalence of one or the other has been suggested to be more closely related to the proximity of specific sources (e.g. wastewater treatment plants, sewage discharges) or the method used than to their distribution within environmental habitats (Boucher and Friot 2017). In order to finally close this gap in microplastics research, it is crucial for the scientific community to adopt a universal and uniform protocol for unbiased sampling of microplastics in the environment. This should be coupled with a consistent approach to identifying and quantifying microplastics sources (i.e. analytical methods for polymers characterization, modelling, the use of natural particles as proxies for the purpose of mapping the distribution of microplastics in the environment). These solutions would lead to a more comprehensive understanding of the quantities, distribution and transformation of primary and secondary microplastics patterns globally and over time.

5. The UN Ocean Decade and microplastics sources control strategies

The identification, investigation and control of microplastics sources to the environment represents a distinct challenge when considered in comparison to the substantial progress that has been made within microplastics research. A significant increase in the number of initiatives aimed at controlling microplastics sources also occurred over the past decade. These initiatives however often remained the domain of a limited group of individuals or organisations, with a narrow focus on specific items or practices (e.g. cigarette butts, single-use straws, clean-up events on sandy/tourist beaches; see for example www.boell.de/en/plasticatlas).

The scientific community, despite significant progress in the field of microplastics research, has yet to make a significant impact on society (Ryan and Chitaka 2022). One of the 10 major challenges identified in the UN Ocean Decade is specifically related to ‘understand ... land- and sea-based sources of pollutants and contaminants and develop solutions to remove or mitigate them’ (<https://oceandecade.org/challenges/>). To approach this challenge, the initiative relies on a number of programmes, projects and contributions (collectively referred to as ‘Actions’) particularly focused on microplastics pollution. Taken together, they have the potential to transform the future of the plastics economy. It is therefore clear that the necessity for a transformation in the life cycle of plastics, encompassing the entire spectrum from source to sink and from production to end consumer, remains a topic of debate even after a decade of being discussed in the 2014 benchmark paper. Should the current trajectory concerning the extraction of raw materials, design and production, packaging and distribution, use, and recycling, reuse, recovery (the 3Rs) or final disposal persist, there is a risk that source control goals will be ultimately missed after the conclusion of the UN Ocean Decade (2030). If source control goals are missed, animals and humans are therefore expected to be exposed to microplastics harm in the future. It is of the utmost importance that the scientific community assumes a collaborative role in providing evidence-based recommendations to policymakers and industries with a view to rethinking the current trends in plastic production and implementing changes to the existing plastic use cycles.

Data availability statement

No new data were created or analysed in this study.

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